

1 **Rapid evolution of a cold stress cline in Mediterranean fruit fly during northward**
2 **range expansion**

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33 **Abstract**

34 The Mediterranean fruit fly, *Ceratitis capitata* (Diptera: Tephritidae), holds an
35 impressive record of successful invasion events promoted by globalization in fruit
36 trade and human mobility. In addition, *C. capitata* is gradually expanding its
37 geographic distribution to cooler temperate areas of the Northern Hemisphere. Cold
38 tolerance of *C. capitata* seems to be a crucial feature that promotes population
39 establishment and hence invasion success. The importance of rapid evolution of traits
40 and their phenotypic plasticity, or alternative processes, in facilitating this invasion is
41 however poorly determined. To tackle this question, here we determined (a) the
42 supercooling capacity (SCP) of immature stages and adults as a measure of cold
43 tolerance, and (b) the acute cold stress survival of adults of *C. capitata* from
44 populations originating from a wide geographical range in the Northern Hemisphere:
45 Austria (Vienna), Croatia (Zaton), Greece (Thessaloniki, Volos, Chania, Heraklion), and
46 Israel (South Arava). To assess the phenotypic plasticity in these populations, (c) the
47 effect of acclimation to low temperatures on acute cold stress survival in adults was
48 also examined. Population and sex were not significant predictors of the SCP of adults.
49 On the other hand, there was marked geographical variation in the SCP of larvae with
50 those originating from Thessaloniki (Greece) and Zaton (Croatia) expressing the
51 highest and the lowest SCP values, respectively. Acclimation at low temperatures was
52 positively related with survival to acute cold stress. Adults from the warmer
53 environment of South Arava (Israel) were less tolerant of acute cold stress compared
54 with those from Heraklion and Thessaloniki. Plastic responses to cold acclimation were
55 population specific with the South Arava population expressing lower levels compared
56 to the two Greek populations. From these data, it seems that northward range
57 expansions have resulted in the rapid evolution of a cold tolerance cline, even among
58 closely related populations or nearby localities, or despite high gene flow among
59 populations that correlate with low temperatures in the region. These results set the
60 stage for asking questions regarding the evolutionary adaptive processes that
61 facilitate range expansions of *C. capitata* into cooler temperate areas of Europe.

62 **Keywords:** *Ceratitis capitata*, supercooling capacity, cold response, cold treatment,
63 dispersal potential, biological invasions

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70 **1 Introduction**

71 Dispersal into new environments is considered to be a key process in the
72 response of insect populations to rapidly changing environmental conditions (Ben-
73 Yosef et al., 2021). Once species become introduced to a new habitat, either
74 accidentally or intentionally, that may present climatic conditions different from those
75 prevailing in the native range, they have to survive and reproduce before starting to
76 spread (Blackburn et al., 2011; Hill et al., 2017). Insects may survive this introduction
77 event by having greater environmental tolerance or by rapidly adjusting performance
78 (i.e., phenotypic plasticity) in that new environment to maximize fitness, or perhaps
79 by some combination of both. Phenotypic plasticity – a trait's response to
80 environmental conditions or a gene-by-environment interaction - may vary among
81 different populations and in response to different environmental characteristics
82 (Gray, 2013) and is a major element that allows insects to cope with more extreme
83 temperatures (Bowler and Terblanche, 2008; Angilletta, 2009). Hence, insects typically
84 adjust their phenotype in response to environmental cues (Rodrigues and Beldade,
85 2020). In the case of thermal stress, insect populations can shift their thermal niche
86 substantially by variation in their phenotypic plasticity to similar conditions (Bujan et
87 al., 2020). Understanding how insects adapt to changing environments is important to
88 assess their ecological and evolutionary dynamics, and predict population resilience
89 to climate change (Oostra et al., 2018). Moreover, it is clear that insects can rapidly
90 adapt through genetic processes (e.g. assimilation, mutation) to novel conditions
91 (Garnas, 2018) to have greater fitness in what would have otherwise been sub-optimal
92 conditions (Hoffmann and Sgrò, 2011).

93 Thermal acclimation is a form of plasticity that can enhance resistance to
94 environmental stress (Terblanche and Hoffmann, 2020), although the potential fitness
95 benefits depend on a range of factors, including the predictability and timing or
96 duration of environmental change (DeWitt and Scheiner, 2004; Jr and Angilletta,
97 2009). Even small changes in a few traits could produce enhanced fitness in certain
98 environments. In cases temperature changes are predictable and endure for some
99 time, insects may use external cues to change their internal condition (Niehaus et al.,
100 2012). Hence, seasonal adjustments (e.g. acclimatization such as overwintering)
101 would be beneficial when insects occur in an environment where the extent of change
102 is predictable with some reliability (Gabriel et al., 2005), and the “costs” are relatively
103 limited. On the other hand, genotypes that express a generalized phenotype will be
104 preferred when environmental temperature varies unpredictably (Gabriel et al.,
105 2005). From the above, it is clear that adaptation to different environmental (thermal)
106 conditions can involve changes in plasticity among individuals, populations, and
107 species (Kingsolver and Buckley, 2018).

108 Temperature affects a range of biochemical and physiological processes, and
109 is one of the most important environmental factors, affecting insects population

110 dynamics (Li et al., 2021). Insects from temperate, polar and/or high-altitude
111 environments must survive the low temperatures they periodically encounter in their
112 habitat in order to persist and thrive (Sinclair et al., 2015). The cold hardiness of insects
113 may help classify species into the major categories of chill susceptible, freeze avoidant
114 and freeze tolerant (Sinclair et al., 2015). Defining the category of cold hardiness for a
115 species sets the stage for measuring lethal temperatures and a comprehensive
116 assessment of mechanisms involved. Parameters used to estimate the tolerance of
117 organisms to extreme temperatures include (a) upper and lower critical thermal limits
118 for activity (CT_{min} & CT_{max}), (b) lethal thermal limits (LTL), (c) knock down resistance,
119 chill coma recovery time (CCR), and (d) supercooling point (SCP). These parameters
120 can be evaluated under chronic or acute conditions using diverse methodology
121 (Beitinger and Lutterschmidt, 2011; Lee Jr et al., 1987; Marshall and Sinclair, 2012;
122 Sinclair et al., 2003). Moreover, the capacity of these traits to adjust in response to
123 changes in environmental conditions (e.g. cold hardening, seasonal acclimatization)
124 provides insight into the plasticity of these traits to contribute to persistence.

125 The supercooling point (SCP) measures the temperature at which an insect's
126 body fluids begin to freeze (Denlinger and Lee Jr, 2010; Maes et al., 2012). Although
127 the SCP helps identifying physiological boundaries (Renault et al., 2002), it is not an
128 indicator of cold hardiness alone because it cannot determine the effect of long-term
129 exposure to cold temperatures above absolute thermal minima (Maes et al., 2012;
130 Renault et al., 2002). Typically, insects exhibit seasonal patterns of supercooling
131 capacity as they adjust physiologically for winter (Lee et al., 1996). For chill susceptible
132 insects, the SCP is lowered in preparation for winter (Lee et al., 1996). Although a
133 variety of factors affect SCP, such as life stage, physiology and sex (Andreadis and
134 Athanassiou, 2017), it is generally accepted that reductions in SCP in response to cold
135 conditions might be adaptive because it slows the rate of ice formation and allows
136 chill susceptible insects to adjust to stresses associated with freezing (Lee et al., 1996).
137 Survival at low temperatures is another aspect of an insect's cold hardiness response
138 (Matsukura et al., 2014), and can be especially informative if coupled with measures
139 of SCP. Factors that affect cold hardiness encompass developmental life stage,
140 behavior, thermal history (e.g. acclimation status, or seasonal acclimatization), age,
141 body size and feeding status (Andreadis and Athanassiou, 2017). For example,
142 acclimation at low temperatures for few days can enhance cold hardiness and enable
143 insects to cope with conditions that would otherwise be lethal (Kristensen et al.,
144 2008).

145 The Mediterranean fruit fly (medfly), *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) (Diptera:
146 Tephritidae), is a highly invasive agricultural pest that has expanded its geographic
147 range from the ancestral habitats of the sub-Saharan Africa to almost all temperate
148 and tropical areas of the globe in less than 200 years (Gomulski et al., 2008). In recent
149 years the species is frequently detected in cooler temperate areas of the Northern

150 Hemisphere. Climate change has been suggested as a factor that may change the
151 geographic limits of this pest, allowing its expansion into temperate areas of Europe
152 (Szyniszewska and Tatem, 2014). On the other hand, physiological, morphological and
153 behavioral attributes enable medfly to survive and reproduce in a wide range of
154 climatic conditions and habitats. Diamantidis et al. (2011), demonstrated that medfly
155 populations originating from geographically isolated regions exhibit a high variation in
156 their life history traits such as longevity or fecundity, which may influence
157 establishment and spread. Understanding the factors that allow *C. capitata* to adjust
158 to such an enormous range of temperature variations may shed additional important
159 light in elucidating the factors that promote its invasion success in cooler areas of
160 central Europe (Nyamukondiwa et al., 2010).

161 A substantial amount of work has been conducted in recent years regarding
162 the thermal tolerance of *C. capitata*, which has mainly focused on the adult stage
163 (Pieterse et al., 2017; Terblanche et al., 2010; Weldon et al., 2018). To the best of our
164 knowledge, SCP has been estimated for different developmental stages of *C. capitata*
165 in only one study (Nyamukondiwa et al., 2013). Furthermore, Nyamukondiwa et al.
166 (2010), demonstrated positive effects of thermal acclimation on the thermal limits of
167 activity in adults (i.e. critical thermal limits). Acclimation to low temperatures
168 generally increases low temperature tolerance, whereas high temperature
169 acclimation improves high temperature tolerance (Whitman and Agrawal, 2009).
170 Nevertheless, there are no studies examining how acclimation to a range of low
171 temperatures can enhance cold tolerance of *C. capitata* in subfreezing temperatures.
172 Furthermore, little is known regarding the response to thermally stressful conditions
173 of geographically distributed *C. capitata* populations, and nothing is known for those
174 populations in the Northern Hemisphere that originate from areas close to the species
175 northern limits of its distribution (Nyamukondiwa and Terblanche, 2009; Weldon et
176 al., 2018).

177 To gain insights on the range expansion of *C. capitata* to more temperate areas
178 of Europe, we determine the SCP and acute cold stress survival of populations
179 obtained from the Northern Hemisphere but reared under 'common-garden' (i.e.,
180 similar) conditions. Cold tolerance of *C. capitata* seems to be a crucial feature that
181 promotes population establishment and hence invasion success. In this study we
182 determined (a) the supercooling capacity (SCP) of immature stages and adults as a
183 measure of cold tolerance, and (b) the acute cold stress survival of adults of *C. capitata*
184 from populations originated from a wide geographical range in the Northern
185 Hemisphere: Austria (Vienna), Croatia (Zaton), Greece (Thessaloniki, Volos, Chania,
186 Heraklion), and Israel (South Arava). To assess the phenotypic plastic capacity in these
187 populations, (c) the effect of acclimation to low temperatures on acute cold stress
188 survival in adults was also examined. We also discuss these data in the context of local
189 climate conditions for each population.

190

191 **2 Materials and Methods**

192 **2.1 Populations**

193 Seven *C. capitata* populations originating from Greece (Thessaloniki, Volos,
194 Chania, Heraklion), Croatia (Zaton), Austria (Vienna) and Israel (South Arava) were
195 tested (Fig. 1). To avoid latitudinal and altitudinal clines in cold tolerance, all the sites
196 used to collect *C. capitata* populations were within ~29° to 48°N latitude and up to
197 157m altitude (Tonione et al., 2020). Köppen-Geiger has classified the climate of
198 Vienna as temperate oceanic (Cfb) with average temperature of the warmest month
199 below 22°C and of the coldest above 0°C (Beck et al., 2018). Zaton's climate is classified
200 as warm temperate, and according to Köppen-Geiger the climate is humid subtropical
201 (Cfa). The average temperature in Zaton is 13,4°C. Regarding Greek populations, the
202 climate is classified as Mediterranean (Csa) except for Thessaloniki. In Thessaloniki the
203 climate is classified as cold semi-arid (Bsk), and the winters are wet while summers
204 are hot and dry. During winter, the average temperature for four months is above
205 10°C, while the coldest above 0°. The Israeli location is between the hot and arid
206 southern part of West Asia, and the northern Mediterranean region, which is cooler
207 and wetter. The climate of the Southern Arava is characterized as extremely hyper-
208 arid climate (Bwh) (Bruins, 2012). Summers in Yotvata are hot and dry, while winters
209 are mild with rainfall characteristic of arid regions, varying among the years. Hence,
210 the Southern Arava population in this study, represents a climatic edge population in
211 the temperate zone of the Northern Hemisphere, and Vienna a range – edge
212 population in the highest latitude of *C. capitata* highest distribution (Papadopoulos et
213 al., 2022). The climatic data of the sites used to collect different populations are
214 represented in Supplementary Tables (S1).

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216 **2.2 Insect Rearing**

217 The experiments were conducted in the laboratory of Entomology and
218 Agricultural Zoology at the University of Thessaly during September 2019 – August
219 2021, at 25±1°C, 45–55% relative humidity and 14:10 L:D photoperiod (photo phase
220 started at 07:00 h). Light was provided by daylight fluorescent tubes and by natural
221 light with the intensity inside the rearing cages ranging from 1500 to 2000 Lux. Pupae
222 from Croatia, Austria and Israel were transported by courier to our laboratory in Volos,
223 Greece. Approximately 500 – 1000 pupae from each location were used to establish
224 experimental colonies in the laboratory. The F₁ – F₆ generations were used to execute
225 the laboratory trial. The Greek populations was derived from field-infested peaches
226 collected around Thessaloniki, and infested oranges from Volos, Chania, and
227 Heraklion. The South Arava (Israel) colony was derived from field- infested

228 pomegranate fruits collected in Yotvata, Israel in December 2020, and augmented (F1)
229 on persimmon The Croatia colony derived from field infested figs from Zaton, (close
230 to Dubrovnik), and the Austria colony derived from field infested pome fruit collected
231 from Vienna.

232

233 **Figure 1:** Locations in the Mediterranean and Central Europe where *Ceratitidis capitata*
234 population that used in the current study originated.

235 Colonies from the different populations were maintained in wooden frame,
236 wire-mesh cages under constant density (100 adults per 30 x 30 x 30 cm cage) in
237 common conditions. Flies were provided with water and a standard adult diet,
238 consisting of a mixture of yeast hydrolysate, sugar, and water (YS) at 1:4:5 ratio,
239 respectively. Females were allowed to lay eggs on red, hollow, perforated plastic
240 domes (5.5-cm-diameter) that was fitted in the lid of a plastic petri dish. The base of
241 the petri dish was partially filled with water to maintain humidity, and 0.5 mL cup filled
242 with orange juice as an oviposition stimulator. Domes were exposed in the rearing
243 cages for 24h, and the collected eggs were used to establish and maintain the
244 respective colony. Eggs (50-100) were seeded in the artificial diet (50g sugar, 50 g
245 brewer's yeast, 25g soybean flour, 1g salt mixture, 4g ascorbic acid, 4g citric acid, 0,75
246 g sodium propionate and 250ml water).

247 To determine the supercooling point (SCP), the lowest temperature before an
248 exothermic reaction indicating the freezing of body fluids, third instar larvae, pupae
249 (1-day and 5-day old) and adults (5-days old) were assessed. A wild population
250 originated from field infested fruit was used from the area of Thessaloniki. The F₁-F₆

laboratory generations of the other six populations were used (the South Arava corresponded to the F₂-F₆). To determine the SCP the protocol of Hou et al. (2009) was followed. Briefly, 30 individuals of each population and life stage were individually loaded into 1.5 ml microcentrifuge tubes. In each tube we inserted a type-T thermocouple sensor (36 SWG) assuring that the sensor, with the help of a cotton-wool wick, got in direct contact with the body of the loaded individual. All tubes were placed into a plastic bag and then into a refrigerated, circulating programmable bath (Polystat, Cole-Parmer) containing silicon oil. Thermocouples were connected to one of two 8-channel Picotech TC-08 (Pico Technology, Cambridge, UK) thermocouple interfaces that precisely recorded temperature at 1 Hz using the PicoLog software. Experiments were initiated at 15°C, held for 5 minutes to equilibrate, and then the temperature programmed to decrease at a rate of 0.23°C/min.

2.3 Survival of adults to acute cold stress (ACS)

To determine the lower lethal temperature that kills 50% of individuals (LLT50) we conducted preliminary trials to determine the mortality rates of adult *C. capitata*. Flies were exposed for 1h at a range of low temperatures (-8, -6, -5, -4, -2, -3 °C) in a programmable water bath with ramping rate of 0.25°C/min. After exposure to the previous mentioned temperatures, survival was recorded after 24, and 48 hours. Using a probit analysis, the LLT50 was estimated at -5.5°C.

To estimate the acute cold stress (ACS), 5-day-old adults (males and females) that were acclimated at either 10, 20, or 30°C for 5 consecutive days were subjected to a standard cold stress of -5.5°C for 1h. We used the following population: Thessaloniki-Greece (F₂-F₃), Heraklion-Greece (F₃) and South Arava-Israel (F₄). Flies from each population and acclimation regimes were randomly distributed in 10 replicates of 10 individuals each (5 males and 5 females) and were subjected to acute cold stress (-5.5°C for 1h) using 10 glass vials for each replication. Following exposure at -5.5°C for 1h, adults were transferred back to 25 °C, placed in plexiglass cages with access to ample food and water, and checked for survival 24 and 48 h later. Survival was defined as a coordinated response to mild stimulation or other normal behaviors such as walking, flying, and feeding.

281

2.4 Data analysis

Data were checked for normality and equality of variance using the Shapiro-Wilk and the Levene test respectively. ANOVA was used to analyze effects of populations, sex, and age on the SCP. The Tukey's HSD post hoc test was used to separate statistically heterogeneous groups ($\alpha=0.05$). The effects of population, thermal acclimation treatment, sex and recovery time and their interactions on adult survival to acute cold stress were assessed by generalized linear models (GLMs), with

289 a binomial distribution and logit-link function for proportions outcome (i.e. number of
290 dead/alive flies). Bonferroni's test was applied to adjust for multiple comparisons. In
291 all tests the significance level was set at $\alpha=0.05$.

292 **3 Results**

293 **3.1 Supercooling point**

294 The SCP of L₃ larvae varied greatly among populations ($F=10.724$, $df = 6$, $P <$
295 0.001) (Fig. 2A, Table 1). Pairwise comparisons revealed that SCP of larvae (L₃) from
296 Zaton was lower (-21.09 ± 0.4 °C) than that from all other populations ($P<0.001$,
297 Bonferroni test). On the other hand, larvae from Thessaloniki had the highest SCP ($-$
298 17.12 ± 0.5 °C) compared to all tested populations (Fig. 2A). Larvae from Zaton had
299 significant lower SCP than those of larvae from Volos ($P<0.001$, Bonferroni test), S.
300 Arava ($P=0.012$, Bonferroni test) and Heraklion ($P=0.003$, Bonferroni test), and
301 marginally lower than that of larvae from Vienna ($P=0.063$, Bonferroni test) (Fig. 2A).
302 For pupae stage, SCP among populations differ marginally only between Thessaloniki
303 and South Arava ($P=0.048$) while pupae age ($F=374.489$, $df =1$, $P<0.001$) and their
304 interaction ($F=11.709$, $df=1$, $P<0.001$) were significant predictors of SCP (Fig. 2B, Table
305 1). Regardless of the population, 1-day old pupae expressed higher SCP compared to
306 5-days old ones, except for pupae from S. Arava. The SCP of young pupae (1d old)
307 ranged between -19.71 ± 0.2 °C (South Arava) and -17.94 ± 0.1 °C (Thessaloniki), while
308 that of old pupae (5d old) from -21.08 ± 0.1 °C (Heraklion) to -19.99 ± 0.1 °C (South
309 Arava) (Fig. 2B). The supercooling points (SCPs) of adults is shown in Fig. 2C. There was
310 a significant difference in SCP among populations ($F=4.125$, $df =6$, $P=0.001$), as
311 opposed between sex ($F=0.243$, $df =1$, $P=0.623$) (Table 1). Flies from Vienna had
312 significant higher SCP than that of flies from Thessaloniki ($P=0.003$, Bonferroni test)
313 and S. Arava ($P=0.006$, Bonferroni test). SCP ranged from -17.47 ± 0.2 °C (Vienna) to -
314 18.95 ± 0.1 °C (Thessaloniki) (Fig. 2C).

316

317 **Figure 2:** Average supercooling point (SCP) of L₃ larvae (A), pupae (B) and adults (C) of
 318 different *Ceratitis capitata* populations. Different letters stand for significant difference
 319 ($P < 0.005$; Tukey). P value less than 0.001 is designated with three (***) asterisks. P
 320 value more than 0.05 is designated with (ns).

321

322

323 **Table 1:** ANOVA table on the effects of (i) population, (ii) population, age and their
 324 interactions on SCP of pupae and (iii) population, sex and their interactions on
 325 Supercooling point (SCP) of adult of different populations of *Ceratitis capitata*

Source of variance	Sum of squares	df	F	P
<i>(i) Larvae</i>				
Between Population	258.668	6	10.724	<0.001
Within Population	816.043	203		
Total	1074.711	209		
<i>(ii) Pupae</i>				
Intercept	162393,685	1	147237.627	<0.001
Population	13.656	6	2.276	0.056
Age	413.038	1	374.489	<0.001
Population * age	77.486	6	11.709	<0.001
Error	448.895	407		
<i>(iii) Adult</i>				
Intercept	69229.033	1	30541	<0.001
Population	56.102	6	4.125	<0.001
Sex	0.548	1	0.242	0.623
Population * sex	7.477	6	0.550	0.770
Error	442.013	195		

326

327 **3.2 Response to acute cold stress**

328 Adult response to acute cold stress (mortality rates after exposure at -5.5°C for
 329 1h) was determined by the origin of the *C. capitata* population and acclimation (Table
 330 2). In addition, the recovery time was a significant predictor of adult mortality rates as
 331 well as the interactions between population and acclimation (Table 2). The lowest
 332 survival rates were observed in flies originating from South Arava (Israel) acclimated
 333 at 30 and 20°C, after 24h. The survival rates of flies that had been acclimatized at 10°C
 334 were higher than that of flies that had been acclimated at 30°C, regardless of
 335 population (Figure 3A). Pairwise comparison revealed that, regardless of the
 336 acclimation, sex and the recovery time, adults from the South Arava population

337 expressed the lowest survival rates, followed by those of Heraklion, Thessaloniki and
 338 Benakeio ($P < 0.036$, Bonferroni test) with no differences between the last two
 339 ($P = 0.292$, Bonferroni test).

340

341 **Figure 3.** (A) Response to acute cold stress of adults from four *Ceratitidis capitata*
 342 populations following different acclimation regimes (30, 20, 10, 25°C [control] for 5

343 days). (B) Predicted death probabilities following a GLM logistic regression analysis
344 model analysis (see Table 2). Acclimated and control flies were subjected to -5.5°C for
345 1h. Mortality was assayed at 24 and 48h after the cold shock. N = 50 males and 50
346 females per treatment.

347 **Table 2.** Results of the generalized linear model (GLMs) testing the effects of
348 population, acclimation, sex, and recovery time on survival rates of *Ceratitis capitata*
349 adults following an acute cold stress at -5.5°C for 1h

Source of variation	Wald χ^2	df	P
Intercept	146.492	1	<0.001
Population	88.610	2	<0.001
Acclimation	187.034	1	<0.001
Sex	0.198	1	0.656
Recovery time	28.076	1	<0.001
Population * Acclimation	142.232	2	<0.001
Population * recovery time	4.547	2	0.103
Population*sex	4.437	2	0.109
Acclimation * recovery time	8.051	1	0.005
Acclimation * sex	1.465	1	0.226

350

351 **4. Discussion**

352 Our results demonstrate that the SCP differed among developmental stages
353 and among populations for specific developmental stages, such as larvae and adults
354 of *C. capitata*, from populations sourced in the Northern Hemisphere. Adults express
355 the highest SCP and pupae (1d old) the lowest one. Older pupae and adults seem to
356 have similar SCP in all studied populations. Adult survival after acute cold stress
357 differed among the four populations tested suggesting that geographical origin of
358 population may affect its cold tolerance. The South Arava population was the least
359 tolerant to cold stress. Moreover, there was a strong association between the
360 acclimation regime and cold tolerance of the different medfly populations. Especially,

361 populations acclimated in low temperatures were more cold tolerant than those
362 acclimated in warmer temperatures.

363 **4.1 Differences among developmental stages**

364 In agreement with our results, an earlier study on *C. capitata* from South Africa
365 revealed that SCP differs among life stages. Nyamukondiwa et al. (2013) reported that
366 pupae expressed the lowest SCP (-19.5 °C), a result that agrees with our findings (SCP
367 of pupae was -20.76 °C). Adults expressed the highest SCP, followed by larvae and
368 pupae. The content of the alimentary channel (e.g. food, symbiotic bacteria) may be
369 involved in ice formation and hence may explain the differences we found among the
370 developmental stages (Tanaka and Udagawa, 1993). The importance of the gut
371 contents as source of ice nucleators had been demonstrated in other species too
372 (Tanaka, 1994). The complete absence of nucleating agents either in the gut,
373 hemolymph or other fluid compartments, may explain the lower SCP of pupae
374 (Renault et al., 2002). Likewise, the empty gut of the ready to pupate L₃ medfly larvae
375 that used in the current study may justify the lower SCP point than those of adults.
376 The lowest among stages SCP of pupae may be explained considering that bare pupae
377 in the soil is a common overwintering stage of *C. capitata* in cooler areas.
378 Furthermore, chemical changes in hemolymph compositions to increase polyols may
379 be associated with different SCPs among developmental stages (Overgaard et al.,
380 2005). Polyols (glycerol, ribitol, sorbitol, myo-inositol etc.), are cryoprotectants that
381 are synthesized by insects in order to survive in low temperatures (Storey and Storey,
382 1991). *Ceratitis capitata* accumulate those cryoprotectants during overwintering to
383 increase the chance of winter survival (Denlinger, 2002).

384 Considering adults, sex was not a predictor of SCP. To the best of our
385 knowledge, there are no studies on Tephritidae which examine the effect of sex on
386 this aspect of cold hardiness. This lack of sex-related variation in SCP suggests that
387 controlling for gender in SCP assays in these species might not be necessary. Hence,
388 possible sex-specific differences might require further study and exploration of
389 additional behavioral and physiological factors such as ageing, mating, and feeding
390 status (Renault et al., 2002).

391 **4.2 Difference among populations in SCP**

392 Differences among populations in SCP were detected in the larval and adult
393 stage. Larvae from the Zaton (Croatia) population exhibited the lowest SCP. This
394 difference may be related to cold adaptation of the specific population considering
395 that it comes from a northern and concurrently cooler area. The supercooling point
396 tends to be lower for population's obtained from higher latitudes and cooler areas
397 (Tanaka, 1996). Regarding adults, climatic variation did not affect the SCP since the
398 Vienna population showed lower SCP than that of flies from Thessaloniki and S. Arava.

399 Those results, suggest that the physiological basis of this phenomena requires further
400 investigation.

401 **4.3 Effect of acclimation on acute cold stress**

402 The second objective of the present study was to examine how acclimation can
403 affect the cold tolerance. Until now, numerous studies have shown how acclimation
404 to low temperatures can increase different metrics of cold hardiness and cold
405 tolerance of diverse insects, such as supercooling point and critical thermal limits (e.g.,
406 limits to activity or loss of neuromuscular function) as well as cold tolerance (Enriquez
407 and Colinet, 2019; Jakobs et al., 2015). Our results revealed that survival rates of flies
408 that have been acclimated at 10°C were higher than that of flies acclimated at 30°C.
409 This comes in agreement with earlier studies suggesting that acclimation at low
410 temperatures can enhance cold tolerance of medfly adults (Basson and Terblanche,
411 2010; Nyamukondiwa and Terblanche, 2009; Terblanche et al., 2010; Weldon et al.,
412 2018), as well as other species of insects. For example, Tarapacki et al. (2021) found
413 that the distribution of *Drosophila suzukii* is closely related with its ability to withstand
414 cold stress. In this study, flies were acclimated at 15, 19 or 23°C and then exposed to
415 a range of low temperatures for different durations. The results revealed that effects
416 of acclimation were noticeable, significantly increasing cold tolerance in their model
417 organism. Cold acclimation increased cold tolerance by almost 1°C per 1°C of
418 decreased acclimation temperature.

419 From the above it is obvious that cold tolerance is highly plastic in *C. capitata*,
420 which could in part explain the fly's success at overwintering, a conclusion that is in
421 agreement with earlier studies in South Africa that performed comparison of closely
422 related species as well (Pieterse et al., 2017; Terblanche et al., 2010). The proposed
423 mechanisms explaining this phenotypic plasticity include: a) protection against cold
424 induced ion and water balance disturbance, b) resistance against oxidative stress, c)
425 management of metabolic balance favoring cold tolerance, d) alterations to
426 membrane fluidity to maintain cellular integrity, etc. (MacMillan et al., 2016). The
427 mechanism conferring this plasticity to medfly are currently unknown and require
428 further study.

429 **4.4 Response of different populations to acute cold stress**

430 Our results revealed that medfly populations originating from different
431 geographic areas respond differently to exposure at a sub-zero temperature for one
432 hour. Differences among geographic populations in their tolerance to subfreezing
433 temperatures may be related to the selection of physiological and metabolic traits apt
434 to the prevailing climatic regimes in the area of origin. Flies originating from South
435 Arava, were the more sensitive to subfreezing temperatures. Greek populations
436 (Thessaloniki, Heraklion) were more tolerant to cold treatment when compared to
437 South Arava flies. Of interest is that the Thessaloniki population (the more Northern

438 population in Greece) and the Heraklion population (the most Southern population in
439 Greece) did not show significant differences in their tolerance to subfreezing
440 temperatures. Papadopoulos et al. (1996) have studied the overwintering capacity of
441 medfly in northern Greece for three winters, and the results showed that *C. capitata*
442 overwinters almost exclusively in the larval stage followed by pupae in early spring.
443 Hence, low winter temperatures determine the end of adult activity in Thessaloniki.
444 Likewise, the period of flight activity becomes longer in warmer, more southern areas
445 (Katsoyannos et al., 1998; Papadopoulos et al., 2001). In southern Greece a small
446 number of adults might be active during winter. Thus, the population from Heraklion
447 might experience low winter temperatures in the adult stage and may be more or
448 equally cold tolerant compared to that from Thessaloniki that experience low
449 temperatures at the larval stage. This among population variation likely has a genetic
450 basis according to Anderson et al. (2005), and reveals that cold tolerance of medfly
451 varies among populations in several thermal stress resistance traits, as shown in
452 medfly for lower critical thermal limits (Weldon et al., 2018). This plasticity may be
453 influenced by larval rearing conditions as well as the thermal experience of adults
454 (Rako and Hoffmann, 2006; Ransberry et al., 2011). A global meta-analysis of critical
455 thermal limits has shown that lower limits are generally more plastic than upper
456 critical limits, and that development may be a key factor in enhancing thermal-
457 acclimation induced plasticity (Weaving et al., (In Press)). This comes in agreement
458 with Weldon et al. (2018) who studied the geographic variation in climate stress
459 resistance among southern African populations. Temperature seasonality seemed to
460 be positively related with lower thermal limits, while upper thermal limits were not
461 affected by bioclimatic variables. Moreover, publication bias suggests effects of
462 plasticity are perhaps somewhat overestimated partly owing to missing negative
463 results, calling for detailed reporting on cold stress plasticity from diverse geographic
464 regions.

465 The difference in cold resistance among populations originated from different
466 climates and latitudes is consistent with results for other species too (Hoffmann and
467 Watson, 1993). Ayrinhac et al. (2004), studied whether population origin determines
468 the cold adaption of *Drosophila melanogaster*. The results showed that recovery after
469 a cold shock at 0°C, was faster for populations living at high latitudes under temperate
470 climates than tropical populations. Populations from southern areas in the Northern
471 Hemisphere, are expected to have experienced warmer conditions compared to those
472 from northern latitudes. Mild temperatures in south temperate habitats result in
473 higher winter mean temperatures (Sinclair and Chown, 2005), hence, variations in
474 temperature affect the frequency with which the freezing threshold is crossed. Also,
475 populations coming from higher latitudes tend to have broader thermal tolerances
476 (thermal breadth) than those originating from lower latitudes (Chown et al., 2002).

477 **4.5 Effect of sex on acute cold stress**

478 Response to acute cold stress did not differ between males and females,
479 regardless the acclimation temperature or population. These results, come in
480 agreement with Nyamukondiwa and Terblanche (2010), who found no gender
481 differences in CTmax and CTmin of *C. capitata*, when they tested different adult ages.
482 On the other hand, Pujol-Lereis and colleagues found that females had higher mean
483 variability of chill coma recovery time than males (Pujol-Lereis et al., 2014). From the
484 above it is clear that males and females may respond similarly regarding certain traits
485 of thermal tolerance such as critical thermal limits, and differently in others such as
486 SCP or CCR time. This variation in the adult stage suggests that individuals may differ
487 in resistance to stress conditions as a result of environmental variation (Vaupel et al.,
488 1979).

489 **5. Conclusions**

490 Understanding the cold tolerance strategy is essential for predicting the
491 potential geographical range of *C. capitata*, particularly in an era of rapid climate
492 change. The results of the present study have broad implications for understanding
493 the phenotypic plasticity of medfly. Further studies on the potential for adaptation to
494 novel environments are vital to understanding the complex effects of global warming
495 on the persistence of medfly populations along elevational gradients.

496

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498 **Declarations**

499 All data will become available up-on request and will be uploaded in an open access
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712

713 **Supplementary Files**714 Supplementary Table 1: Climatic data from different *Ceratitis capitata* collection sites715 (<https://en.climate-data.org>)

Vienna	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Avg. Temp. °C	0	1.6	5.6	11.1	15.5	19.5	21.4	21	16.1	11	6.1	1.2
Min. Temp. °C	-2.9	-2	0.8	5.7	10.4	14.3	16.4	16	11.9	7.2	3.1	-1.5
Max. Temp. °C	3 °C	5.4	10.3	16.1	20.1	24.1	26	25.7	20.5	15	9.2	4.1
Precipitation mm	39	37	52	51	75	79	82	72	74	50	49	43
Humidity (%)	79	75	71	65	67	65	64	65	71	78	81	81
Rainy days (d)	7	6	8	7	9	9	9	7	7	7	7	7

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Zaton	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Avg. Temp. °C	5.7	6.3	9.7	13.8	18	22.4	24.9	24.9	20.1	15.8	11.6	7.3
Min. Temp. °C	2.6	2.9	6	9.9	14.1	18.2	20.6	20.6	16.5	12.6	8.8	4.4
Max. Temp. °C	8.9	9.6	13.2	17.1	21.2	25.6	28.3	28.4	23.6	19.1	14.4	10.2
Precipitation mm	103 (4)	101 (3)	94 (3)	100 (3)	88 (3)	53 (2)	35 (1)	49 (1)	107 (4)	137 (5)	178 (7)	140 (5)
Humidity (%)	75%	73%	72%	71%	71%	67%	63%	64%	68%	74%	76%	75%
Rainy days (d)	8	7	7	8	6	5	3	4	6	7	10	9

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Thessaloniki	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Avg. Temp. °C	4.2	6.1	9.7	14.1	19.3	24 °	26.6	26.	21.5	16	10.9	5.5
Min. Temp. °C	0.7	2.1	5.3	9.6	14.8	19.3	21.8	21.9	17.2	12.2	7.5	2.3 F
Max. Temp. °C	8.3	10.5 F	14.3	18.6	23.7	28.5	31.3	31.2 °	25.9	20.1	14.8	9.5
Precipitation mm	53	50	60	59	71	52	46	46	53	61	63	73
Humidity (%)	77%	73%	71%	68%	64%	58%	53%	56%	64%	73%	76%	78%
Rainy days (d)	6	6	7	7	7	6	5	5	5	5	6	6

718

719

Volos	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Avg. Temp. °C	5.9	6.7	9.5	12.8	17.7	22.2	24.7	24.6 °	20.6	16.1	11.8	7.5
Min. Temp. °C	3	3.6	5.9	9.1	13.8	18.3	20.9	21.2	17.7	13.5	9.2	4.9
Max. Temp. °C	8.7	10	13.2	16.6	21.4	25.8	28.2	28	23.7	19 °	14.6 °	10.1
Precipitation mm	104	88	84	42	45	20	27	32	64	92	88	116
Humidity (%)	77%	74%	71%	69%	65%	59%	56%	59%	68%	75%	78%	79%
Rainy days (d)	8	8	7	5	4	3	2	3	5	7	7	9
720												

Chania	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Avg. Temp. °C	10.4	10.5	12.2	14.6	18.3	22.2	24.7	24.8 °	22.2	18.8	15.5	12.1
Min. Temp. °C	8.7	8.7	10.1	12.2	15.6	19.4	21.7	22.1	19.9	16.9	13.7	10.5
Max. Temp. °C	12	12.2	14.2	16.7	20.4	24.4	26.9	26.8 °	24.3	20.6	17.2	13.6
Precipitation mm	156	140	88	39	26	6	3	6	27	82	109	171
Humidity (%)	77%	75%	73%	70%	66%	62%	60%	63%	68%	73%	75%	77%
Rainy days (d)	11	10	8	4	3	1	1	1	3	7	8	12
721												

Heraklion	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Avg. Temp. °C	10.1	10.5 °	12.5	15.6	19.8	23.8	25.9	25.6	23.1	19.1 °	15.3	11.7
Min. Temp. °C	7.3	7.3	8.5	11.1	15	19.1	21.5	21.6	19.2	15.8	12.4	9.1
Max. Temp. °C	13.4	14.2	16.9	20.4	24.8	28.6	30.4	30.1	27.6	23.1	19	14.9
Precipitation mm	72			37	32	13	4	6	21	38	45	69
Humidity (%)	81%	78%	72%	64%	58%	53%	53%	58%	64%	72%	77%	82%
Rainy days (d)	9	8	6	4	3	2	1	1	3	5	5	8
722												

South Arava	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Avg. Temp. °C	11.3	13.	16.7	20.7	24.8	27	28.6	28.3	26	22.7	17.5	12.7
Min. Temp. °C	6	7.2	10	13.4	17.4	19.6	21.3	21.3	19.3	16.9	11.9	7.3
Max. Temp. °C	16.7	19.1	23.1	27.5	31.7	34.2	35.7	35.4	32.8	28.	23.3	18.3
Precipitation mm	13	11	8	2	1	0	0	0	0	2	3	6
Humidity (%)	55%	47%	38%	31%	29%	32%	35%	39%	44%	46%	48%	53%
Rainy days (d)	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1

723 *Data: 1991 - 2021 Min. Temperature °C (°F), Max. Temperature °C (°F), Precipitation / Rainfall

724 mm (in), Humidity, Rainy days.

725